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THE ISSUES OF USING FOLK DANCES IN SAID RUSTAMOV'S SUITES

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ВОПРОСЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ НАРОДНЫХ ТАНЦЕВ В СЮИТАХ САИДА РУСТАМОВА

Abstract.

The presented article is devoted to the study of the use of national dances in the suites of eminent composer, public figure, professor Said Rustamov. During the investigation, it became known that the composer Said Rustamov is the author of several interesting suites for the orchestra of folk instruments. In his "Azerbaijan", "Dance" and "Third" suites all scenes were based on national dance intonations. In these scenes, we came across to the intonations of national dances such as "Terakama", "Uzundera", "Darchini", "Azerbaijan", "Gizilgül" and others. In his suites, the composer managed to professionally combine the elements of national dance with the classical suite form and suite structure. In the suites, the vivid life events, lyrical feelings, the glory of the motherland were represented through dances. Adhering to the classical suite genre, the composer created a close unity of this genre with national musical folklore. In order to make the suites colorful, while repeating the themes, he assigned them sometimes to a group of instruments, and sometimes to individual instruments, and the group of instruments confronts each other and formed dialogues.

Thus, we come to the conclusion that Said Rustamov is the author of several interesting suites for the orchestra of folk instruments. In these suites, the composer adhered to the classical suite genre and managed to create a close unity of this genre with national musical folklore. Said Rustamov's suites for orchestra of folk instruments remain relevant in our modern times and are included in educational programs and concert repertoire.

Аннотация.

Представленная статья посвящена исследованию использования национальных танцев в сюитах выдающегося композитора, общественного деятеля, профессора Саида Рустамова. В ходе исследования стало известно, что композитор Саид Рустамов является автором нескольких интересных сюит для оркестра народных инструментов. В его сюитах «Азербайджан», «Танец» и «Третий» все сцены были основаны на национальных танцевальных элементах. В этих сценах можно наблюдать элементы таких национальных танцев, как «Терекеме», «Узундере», «Дарчини», «Азербайджан», «Гызылгюль» и других. В своих сюитах композитору удалось профессионально объединить элементы национального танца с классической сюитной формой и сюитной структурой. В сюитах яркие события жизни, лирические чувства, слава родины были представлены через танцы. Придерживаясь жанра классической сюиты, композитор создал тесное единство этого жанра с национальным музыкальным фольклором.

Таким образом, приходим к выводу, что Саид Рустамов является автором нескольких интересных сюит для оркестра народных инструментов. В этих сюитах композитор придерживался жанра классической сюиты и сумел создать тесное единство этого жанра с народным музыкальным фольклором. Сюиты для оркестра народных инструментов Саида Рустамова остаются актуальными и в наше время и входят в образовательные программы и концертный репертуар.

Ключевые слова: Танец, Саид Рустамов, «Раст», «Шур», «Чахаргах», мугам, «Кахраманы», «Дилишады», тар, кяманча, оркестр, балабан, народные инструменты.

Keywords: Dance, Said Rustamov, "Rast", "Shur", "Chahargah", mugham, "Kahramany", "Dilshady", tar, kamancha, orchestra, balaban, folk instruments.

Introduction:

The People's artist of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the awardee of the State Prize, public figure, professor Mr. Said Rustamov rendered incomparable services to our musical culture. The composer, who played a great role in the development of our musical art, with his colorful creativity, along with creating beautiful works in various genres collected and immortalized examples of national folklore.

Said Rustamov is the well-known author of the three interesting musical comedies, songs that left an eternal track in the hearts of the people, music for various dramatic works, popular works for the orchestra of folk instruments and song-dance ensemble. He conducted the orchestra of folk musical instruments for many years, and during this period he expanded the composition of the orchestra by deeply mastering the individual characteristics of our national musical

instruments, technical and expressive means, and included them in the score. Along with writing pieces for the orchestra, he expanded the repertoire by transcribing various musical works for the orchestra, and worked tirelessly for the recognition in different countries the folk instruments' orchestra, which is widely active in the cultural life of Azerbaijan. *Professor Abasova wrote: "Composer Said Rustamov, by leaving the deep track, obtained the great achievements in the field of song genre in the musical culture of Azerbaijan. The basis of the composer's style, the formation of the musical language has found its solution in this genre, and these songs praise the hardworking people of our nation, the beauty of our Motherland, and the pure emotions of the youth."* [Abasova, 1973: pp.43-45].

In the years of the post-Great Patriotic War II, the composer Said Rustamov by entering to the period of maturation of his creativity, addressing to the different genres of the music where he desires to reflect the mood of glorious victory and the heroic courage of our nation in his works. He enriches his works with national color by making fuller use of folk music as a source of creativity.

In the "Azerbaijan" suite, which he composed in 1946, he gave ample space to the intonations of the moment, and prominently reflected the lines of a number of genres like jengin, dance, mugam of our national folklore. The program name of the suite was related to the desire to glorify the native land, the closeness of intonation with national dances is noticeable. The "Azerbaijan" suite is being among the works that continues the traditions of U. Hajibeyli, both from the point of view of its structure and from the point of view of the interpretation of the orchestral sounding. Often, these works are considered as a continuation of the traditions of "Chahargah" and "Shur" fantasias composed by U. Hajibeyli for the orchestra of folk instruments [Isazade, 1944: pp.3-4].

It is true to mention that "Azerbaijan" suite can be compared with U. Hajibeyli's fantasias in terms of structure and in other words, the contrasting alternation of lyrical, gentle episodes with the solemn pieces that characterize the hero here, the seriality manifested in the form of a suite, has a certain affinity with the clearly noticeable aspects of U. Hajibeyli's fantasias. Said Rustamov's suites for folk instruments orchestra used original folk melodies. The composer organically combined them with the form and structure of the suite genre, keeping the performance style, manner and character of Azerbaijani folk dances.

In 1944, a contest of anthems dedicated to Azerbaijan was held in our Republic. Although genius Uzeyir Hajibeyli's anthem "Azerbaijan" was the winner of the competition, Said Rustamov's anthem dedicated to Azerbaijan was included in the list of the best works. Two years later, the composer included the same anthem in the final part of the suite and named it as "Azerbaijan". In the Azerbaijani suite, which consists of three parts, the composer created a beautiful unity of the classical suite form with folk dances. Said Rustamov's love for the suite genre is not accidental. The structure of the suite, that is, the alternation of

individual numbers, is characterised of Azerbaijani folk music and dances. The solemn (Maestoso), celebratory, heroic first part is composed in a complexed two-part form, in 4/4 size, and begins with an introduction built on the "Chahargah" chord with the "do" ending. The first part consists of two major episodes: Episodes A and B:

I part A
episode I part B episode
Introduction + II couplet+I
couplet+culmination+ couplet+ chorus
aa+bb,
aa+bb cc+dd

In the first part of the suite, the composer used the intonations of the "Jangi" folk dance and strengthened the solemn mood of the piece. It is known that "Jangi" folk dance is based on "Chahargah" mugham. The introduction of the melody's theme is played by the first kamancha (*The Azerbaijani kamancha is the ancient grandfather of the modern violin. Many believe that the invention of the violin followed the influences of the kamancheh and the lira*) and the first tar (*The Azerbaijani Tar is a long-necked, plucked lute, traditionally crafted, and performed in communities throughout the Republic of Azerbaijan. The tar is featured alone or with other instruments in numerous traditional musical styles.*), while the rest of the groups are accompanied by rhythmic marching chords. This rhythmic structure is repeated in the third part of the suite. The melody of the opening theme played by tar and kamanchas, rests on the tonic, moving up and down in sixteenth notes. The orchestral accompaniment of the first movement of episode A is simple and very sincere, and at the beginning of the second movement the group of tars begin to imitate the wind instruments. In the suite, the composer wanted to create the magnificent sound inherent of a symphony orchestra by assigning solo themes mainly to string instruments. *Professor Abasova wrote: "Said Rustamov continued the traditions of the orchestration of suites of typical symphonic orchestra"* [Абасова, 1975: с.49-52].

Subject B sounds like a continuation of subject A in terms of intonation and rhythm. Firstly, in the second movement the theme is set with minor changes, then by the second, bass strings and balaban (*The wind instrument balaban (also sometimes called as balaman) is widely used in ceremonies. The origin of the word comes from "bala" – little, "ban" – sound of cock-crow*) as continues, and ends with a gamma-various passage of the strings moving upward in sixteenth notes. The orchestral texture is polyphonically enriched by repeating the A theme of the second couplet in unison in an octave cymbal, and imitations between different groups are noticeable. After the second couplet of the A theme, the B theme also ends, and the ascending gamma-like figure of the B theme prepares the connecting theme. The first bars of the closing theme are sequenced in unison by the kamanchas and first tar, the balabans perform the role of orchestral pedals, and other groups accompany the organ score in the background. In the middle of the connecting theme, the size of the piece changes and the orchestra becomes cheerful. Episode A ends with the short motifs of the

opening theme played in imitation between various instruments. By changing tonality, the interpretation of B episode begins. Episode B is similar in rhythm and intonation to episode A, although the character is a bit more refined. Episode B, which consists of a couplet, a chorus, and an ending, begins with a four-bar orchestral introduction. The melody of the d theme, which sounds after the C couplet, is structured in the form of D sequence played by the kamanchas and the first tar. The group of sazs joins the second repetition of the theme in an octave cymbal, and as the theme ends, the tars move up in a gamma-like figure, preparing the finale of the piece. The composer finished the end of the first part with a completely new motive, brought new freshness to this part, and made it colorful in terms of intonation. This work of S. Rustamov can be compared with the fantasies of U. Hajibeyli in terms of the way of using folk music and the creative processing of folklore genre features. However, it is precisely in the field of using folklore sources that one can see a special expansion, comprehensiveness, and the use of new genre "prototypes" in S. Rustamov's suite. For example, in the introduction section and the first part of the suite, selective features typical for the Jangi are noticeable. **The composer S. Rustamov said: "I present the rich dance music of our people through the suite genre"** [Ələsgərov, 1959: s.3-6].

The second part of the suite is a board for the music in 3/4 size, lyrical (Andante cantabile), the reminiscent of a song without lyrics. Here, we hear the intonations of the folk dance the "Kızılgül". The "Kızılgül" folk dance is played over the "Shur" mugam. If we compare the themes of the first part with cheerful, solemn mood and heroic feelings, then the second part can be characterized with lyrical images of love and affection. The second part begins with a four-part orchestral introduction, the piano's quiet, swaying flowing "re" intonation reminds the fluid moment of the "Shur".

In the background of the organ score of the tars, the heart-warming melody of the first balabans moves slowly and steadily. The melody of the chords is played by the pipe (Tutek), the first balaban, the second and bass tars, and the third and fourth balabans keep a homophonic background. The first tars move down the chromatic scale, enriching the work of intonation.

The third final part of the suite has the character of a solemn march, it can also be called an orchestral anthem. In the first A part of the finale, which is composed in a complex three-part form, three themes are united: A(a+b+a). The second part B is divided into three musical phrases. Section A circulates in the "Garay" section of the "Rast" mugham, and in the second sentence, the intonations of the "Maye-Rast" mugham sound like an introduction to an instrumental song. In this part, the composer with applying the intonations of the "Azerbaijan" folk dance once again emphasized the essence of the title of the suite. "Azerbaijan" folk dance is interpreted based on the intonation of the moment of the "Rast". Due to the skillful use of traditional timbres of our folk musical instruments in the orchestration of the suite, the "Azerbaijan" suite fully justified its name and was

included into the history as a clear example of our national music. Oktay Guliyev, who worked as a soloist of the orchestra of folk instruments for many years, greatly appreciates the figurative-emotional content of the "Azerbaijan" suite, as well as the role it plays in the development of professional competence of orchestra musicians, writes: *"Suite's music is mainly cheerful. The composer tried to express the beauty of Azerbaijan, its natural landscapes, charming beauties, the people's life, their wishes and dreams in the language of music with effective colors, and successfully achieved it. In the "Azerbaijani suite" the artistic and technical capabilities and timbre characteristics of the group of instruments included in the orchestra were very well used. In order to clearly show the timbre individuality of folk musical instruments, S. Rustamov gave an ample space to the solo instrument - tar, balaban, tutek, saz, and kamancha. All this plays an important role in making the orchestral palette rich and meaningful. "Azerbaijan Suite" had a great influence on improvement of the collective's performance qualities.* [Quliyev, 1980, s.36-37].

Composer Said Rustamov enriches the music of the suites with national color by making fuller use of folk dances in the suites which he composed for the orchestra of folk instruments. In the suite "Rags", which he composed in 1948, he gives a wide space to the intonations of the moment and clearly reflects the lines of a number of genres and dances of our national folklore. S. Rustamov's familiarity with this folklore materials played an important role in arousing his desire to use the genre features and rhythm intonation aspects of folk dances to a new level. Thus, in the 1930s, S. Rustamov, who actively participated in the work of the Scientific Research Music Cabinet, was engaged in transcribing folk dance melodies, along with other folklore examples, and in 1937 his collection "Azerbaijani Folk Dances" was published. In the process of this work, the composer deeply studied the examples of folk dance music and had the opportunity to get to the intricacies of their melodic and rhythmic features. Therefore, the suites created by S. Rustamov became one of the works that vividly embodied the spirit and artistic aspects of our national dance music in the composer's creativity.

The first part of the three-part "Dance" suite is called "Jidir", the second part is called "Brides", and the third part is called "Yalli". In the dance suite, the content is expressed and are given through dances and the scenes typical to Azerbaijani folk dances. Each of the part is taken purely from folk holiday celebrations and can be called a music board. One of the unique features of the suite is that the three parts sound one after the other without stopping, without a break, and as if one scene is gradually replaced by another scene. The character of the first "Jidir" part reflects the whims of youth, youthful pride, the courage of quick and agile brave youngsters competing with each other, clearly comes in front of our sight. This part begins in a simple two-part form, based on the intonations of the "mi bemol" of the "Rast" moment and the orchestra's performance in the "Allegro" tempo.

In the first part, we hear the intonations of the "Asgarani" folk dance, which is based on the "Rast" moment. Throughout the interpretation of the main theme, the tonic plays an intonationally leading role, and the entire melody revolves around the major third (mi bemol-sol), sometimes including the quintet (mi bemol). Periodic repetition of motifs is characteristic of Azerbaijani folk dances. The composer Suleyman Alasgarov wrote about this: "*National dance elements are very prominent in Said Rustamov's suites for the orchestra of folk instruments. So, typical dance music of S. Rustamov's many times repeats the motifs.*" [Ələsgərov: 1992, s.7-9].

It should be noted that Said Rustamov gave an ample space to the background sound in his suites to create the accompaniment typical to the dance music. This method proves his close connection with the practice of folk performance. Thus, background sound is widely used in ensembles of folk instruments, especially wind ensembles. The first balaban plays the melody, the second balaban prolongs the sound, and the drum provides rhythmic accompaniment.

The second part of the suite, "Gelinler", recalls the calm, lyrical dance of the girls. The music of this part among other dances is close to the folk dance "Uzundare". The composer who addressed to the "Uzundera" folk dance performed as a follower of the traditions of the great Uzeyir Hajibeyli. Thus, the music of the folk dance "Uzundera" was used in U. Hajibeyli's operetta "O olmasin, bu olsun". Thereby, Mashadi Ibad's song "*No matter how old I am*" is based on the melody of the folk dance "Uzundera" [İsazadə, 1981: s.5-29].

The basis of the second part, which contrasts with the first part by its nature, is the theme built on the maye "Shur" moment with the "fa":

The second part begins with a small introduction to the tempo of "Andante gracioso". The melody is played by the first and second balabans and circulates around the tonic chord, quarta (si bemol), quinta (do). The light accompaniment of tars and kamanchas matching the lyrical melody is very selective in its connection.

The episode at the end of the second part sounds like an introduction to the third part, acting as a coda.

Unlike the previous two parts, the third part so-called "Yalli" is built on 4/2 size, which is typical to the Yalli dance. Not only a dance scene is depicted here, but also with a support to a festive celebration a large crowd of people dancing yalli, the national dance. In accordance with the scene, the melody of the yalli is played by the balabans, while the tar group repeats the rhythmic accompaniment of the drum instruments, and the kamancha and the piano perform with short eighth notes. According to its structure, the third part is reminiscent of Azerbaijani drum mughams. U. Hajibeyli wrote about this: "In the "Heyarti" drum mugham vocal improvisation is sometimes accompanied by a rhythmic background, and sometimes alternates with it [Hacıbəyli, 2008: s.544].

The coda of the third part ends with the alternation of the main and auxiliary themes. We mentioned that Said Rustamov is the author of various suites for the

orchestra of folk instruments. The composer did not specifically name the "Third" suite, but presented it as the "Third" suite. The basis of the suite is the images of modern life, depicting dynamic life events. Unlike the previous suite, the third suite is larger. Each of the four parts has a playful tempo (Allegretto), written in full mugham and dance style. The first part "Introduction" is a lyrical mugham improvisation based on the "Shur" mugham and begins with an extensive passage of the orchestra and piano:

Here, we hear the intonations of the folk dance "Kahramani" based on the "Shur" mugham.

In the "Third" suite the composer fills the orchestra with notes in the lower registers of the piano, and at the culmination, the piano plays the theme in chords, supporting the other groups. The melody of the opening theme of the suite is interpreted by the playing of tar and kamanchas. A new theme is heard, stopping on the sixth fret with a half note moving first up and then down. This theme, built on the backing sound "Lya", is played for the second time in the kamancha part, and the orchestral texture is enriched in terms of intonation.

The second part of the "Lyric Song" is different from the lyrical part of the previous suites, revealing clear, bright images along with delicate feelings, and the elements of "Dilshadi" folk dance attract attention in "Shur" mugham.

"Lyric song" is built on the "Shur" chord with "re" sounds under the rhythmic accompaniment of tars, and performed by a solo clarinet. This part of a song character is composed in the form of couplet-variation, and it is possible to find moments taken from the structure of folk songs here.

In the second part the instruments often change their roles, sometimes playing the melody, sometimes accompanying, sometimes keeping a polyphonic background. For example, the melody played first by the solo clarinet changes in intonation and rhythmically, and goes to the playing of the kamanchas, and then the tars. Polyphonic elements are clearly noticeable in the score during the interpretation of the melody in the balabans.

The third part, with a playful tempo, is called "Mezeli raks", where the main theme is a humorous, playful dance. The colorful pages of society, careless life and cheerful dance of girls appear vividly in front of our eyes. In this part, the melody of the folk dance "Tarakama" is applied. Each sentence of the theme, which consists of square-shaped sentences, is made up of four bars, and the melody is played in unison of groups of tars and kamanchas. The group of string instruments plays a leading role in the composer's scores. Propulsive melodies are played in unison of string instruments, which announces the colors of folk music and mugham. In folk instrumental ensembles, the tar and kamancha often sound in unison or the kamancha imitates the part of the tar. In the third part, the humorous melody of the kamanchas and tars is accompanied by the piano, and at the culmination, the texture becomes complex and with timbre rings the orchestra starts playing "Tutti". Professor Ogtay Guliyev wrote: "*Said Rustamov understood the role of*

instruments in the orchestra very well. Because he worked as an orchestra conductor for many years. In the orchestra, he used the entire group of instruments equally and effectively. [Quliyev, 1980: s.22-27].

The third part was composed in a simple three-part form, based on the intonations of the "Shur" moment with the "sol" note. Each sentence of the theme, which consists of square-shaped sentences, is made up of four bars, and the melody is played in unison by tars and kamanchas. The group of string instruments plays a leading role in the composer's scores. Propulsive melodies are played in unison of string instruments, suggesting folk dance music. The fourth part of the suite "Gaitagi" played the role of the finale, it was built on the "Shur" moment with "re" note.

In complex 12\16 size, the sharp tempo (Presto) rhythmically performed by tars in a simple three-part form, enthusiastic and passionate males' dance are depicted, and the intonations of the "Qahramani" folk dance attracts attention. The rhythmic image of the theme is played by the drum instruments. In the mid-part, a new, somewhat lyrical theme performed by kamanchas, plays a counterpoint against the fast-flowing theme of the tars, reminiscent of another group dancing away from everyone else. Two contradicting to each other themes are developed and interfered into the orchestra's performance.

The third suite is another vivid example of Said Rustamov's creative use of genre, metrorhythmic and timbre features of folk dance music. In the second and third parts of the work, the typical aspects of two types of Azerbaijani folk dances - rhythmic lyrical dance and cheerful yally dance - are reflected. The famous composer Agabaji Rzayeva wrote: *"It is possible to find dance intonations that reflect each character in Said Rustamov's suites. The composer created a beautiful and exemplary combination of dance music and classical suite genre"* [Rəhmətov, 1980: s.108].

Thus, in the suites composed by Said Rustamov for the orchestra of folk instruments, hyper life events, lyrical feelings, and the glory of the homeland were represented through dances. Adhering to the classical suite genre, the composer created a close unity of this genre with national musical folklore. In order to make the suites colorful, while repeating the themes, he assigns them sometimes to a group of instruments, and sometimes to individual instruments, and the group of instruments confronts each other and gives dialogues. The timbre of wind instruments is used to express the lyricism of the vocal part. Our national dances are based on the melodic basis of the suites. Taking into account the characteristic features and rhythmic uniqueness of the melody, Said Rustamov managed to create a high sound palette by combining tar with kamancha, saz and balabans. Said Rustamov's suites are included in the teaching repertoire of all higher and secondary music schools in our modern life, these rich works are played in concerts and create conditions to open up for the potential opportunities of performers.

The suites created by S. Rustamov for the orchestra of folk instruments are distinguished by their unique use of the serial structure of national dance creativity in orchestral works. In these works, S.

Rustamov demonstrates his knowledge of the regularity of the folklore examples he refers to, his mastery of using their point-intonation, metrorhythmic, and textural features. There is no doubt that S. Rustamov's activity as a folklorist, the great work he did in the field of collecting folk songs and dances, played a great role for him as a school of studying folk music. On the other hand, the appearance of these works was directly related to the fact that S. Rustamov was a conductor who was well acquainted with the capabilities of the orchestra of folk instruments.

S. Rustamov's creative interaction with folklore music in two fields - folklore studies and conducting folk instrument orchestras - gave its results, and ensured the creation of a whole branch of his creativity as a composer and the sealing his signature in this field.

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